

Sasha Gray is undoubtedly an American adult movie actress, producer, and musician. She was born on March fourteen, 1988 in North Highlands, California. She's five'seven" tall using a slender Make, very long blonde hair, and green eyes.

Gray began her job as an Grownup film actress in 2006 with the age of 18. She swiftly turned one of the most well-liked and sought-after actresses from the business. She gained numerous awards for her performances in Grownup films, such as the AVN Best New Starlet Award in 2008. She has appeared in in excess of 200 adult films, and it has directed numerous of her very own.

Together with her do the job in the adult sector, Grey can also be a musician, creator, and artist. She has launched a number of new music albums, and has composed two books about her experiences from the Grownup industry. She has also appeared in quite a few mainstream movies, including The Girlfriend Experience and Entourage.

Gray has also develop into An effective businesswoman and brand ambassador. She has collaborated with quite a few fashion and Way of living brand names to market their products, and [sasha grey nude](#) has long been featured in advertising and marketing campaigns for models which include Calvin Klein and Adidas.

Gray is renowned for her willingness to push boundaries and split taboos. She is now an icon inside the Grownup field, and an inspiration to lots of.